

A highly selective and sensitive extractive spectrophotometric determination of tin(II) using 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran as a complexing agent

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Abstract : An extractive spectrophotometric method is developed for the trace determination of tin. A yellow 1 : 2 (M : L) complex of tin(II) is formed with 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran (CHPB) in HCl medium. The coloured species is quantitatively extracted into carbon tetrachloride and shows maximum absorbance at 411–417 nm. The method obeys Beer's law in the range 0–2.0 $\mu\text{g Sn}^{\text{II}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$ with molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of $3.92 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0030 \mu\text{g Sn cm}^{-2}$, respectively at 415 nm. The method is highly selective and free from the interference of a large number of elements including platinum metals. It is sensitive, simple, rapid and has been satisfactorily applied to the analysis of various synthetic and technical samples including gun metal.

Keywords : Tin(II), substituted benzopyran, extraction, spectrophotometric determination.

The literature survey on the spectrophotometric methods of determination of tin reveals that the existing methods using dithiol¹, phenylfluorone¹, 2-(5-nitro-2-pyridylazo)-5-[*N*-*n*-propyl-*N*-(3-sulfopropyl)aminophenol]² and potassium ethylxanthate³ as complexing agents in binary complexes and some ternary complexes^{4,5} are generally time consuming as they require 20 s to 30 min for full colour development^{1–4}, non selective as they suffer from the interference of Mo, V, W, Fe, Co, Cu, Bi, Hg, Zr and many other elements and have low sensitivity in most of the cases^{1,3,5}. In continuation of our work on analytical reagents, an attempt has been made to introduce a new benzopyran derivative, 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran (CHPB) for the complexation and extractive spectrophotometric determination of tin which gives a more rapid, highly reproducible and selective method as compared to the existing ones.

Results and discussion

Effect of various organic solvents on the absorbance of tin(II)-CHPB complex : Sn^{II} formed a yellow complex with CHPB in HCl medium which was extracted by various organic solvents namely carbon tetrachloride, toluene, dichloromethane, benzene, isoamylacetate, isobutyl methyl ketone, ethyl acetate, chloroform, cyclohexane, 1,2-dichloroethane and isoamyl alcohol in the decreasing order of the absorbance. Hence, carbon tetrachloride showing maximum and stable absorbance was preferred as the most suit-

able extractant for the metal complex. A single equilibration of the aqueous phase with equal volume (10 ml) of carbon tetrachloride under optimum conditions gave quantitative (100%) recovery of Sn^{II} -CHPB complex.

Table 1. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of Sn-CHPB complex

HCl (M) ^a	0.040	0.042	0.043	0.044	0.045–0.07	0.075
Absorbance	0.240	0.260	0.280	0.300	0.330	0.300
0.2% CHPB (ml) ^b	0.2	0.5	1.0	1.2	1.3–4.5	4.6
Absorbance	0.060	0.170	0.280	0.315	0.330	0.305
Equilibration time (s) ^c	0	1	2	3	4	5–300
Absorbance	0.020	0.050	0.150	0.260	0.300	0.330

^a $\text{Sn}^{\text{II}} = 10 \mu\text{g}$, HCl = variable, CHPB (0.2% (w/v) in acetone) = 1.5 ml, aqueous volume = solvent volume = 10 ml, solvent = carbon tetrachloride, equilibration time = 30 s, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 415 \text{ nm}$; ^bHCl = 0.045–0.07 M, other conditions being the same as in (a) except for the variation in CHPB concentration; also *b* = 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran (CHPB); ^c0.2% CHPB in acetone = 1.5 ml, other conditions being the same as in (b) except for the variation in equilibration time.

The absorbance spectrum of the extracted species in carbon tetrachloride showed that the absorption maximum was in the range 411–417 nm, where the reagent blank had minimal absorbance. In carbon tetrachloride, the absorbance remained constant for more than 72 h.

Effect of concentration of HCl, CHPB and equilibration time on the absorbance of the complex : The optimum val-

Table 2. Comparison of the present method with other methods

Sl. no.	Aqueous conditions	Solvent (λ_{\max})	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$) (Molar absorptivity) ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	Interfering metal ions
1.	Sn^{II} , 0.5–1.0 M H_2SO_4 , thioglycolic acid, 5% gumarabic solution, dithiol solution, colour development time 10 min ^a	– (535)	0 204 (5.8×10^3)	Bi^{III} , Hg^{II} , Ag^{I} , Cd^{II} , Cu^{II} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI}
2.	Sn^{II} , H_2O_2 , gumarabic, phenylfluorone, citrate, pH 1.1 (± 0.1), colour development time 30 min ^a	– (510)	0 0015 (7.7×10^4)	Sb^{III} , Ge^{IV} , Zr^{IV} , Ga^{III} , Fe^{III} , Ta^{V} , Nb^{V} , Mo^{VI} , Ti^{IV}
3.	Sn^{IV} , 1.0 M acetic acid, 2-(5-nitro-2-pyridylazo)-5-[<i>N-n</i> -propyl- <i>N</i> -(3-sulfopropyl)aminophenol], colour development time 5 min ^b	– (580)	0.0015 (7.7×10^4)	–
4.	Sn^{II} , 0.050–0.075 M HCl, potassium ethylxanthate, 20 s waiting time ^c	Chloroform (360)	0 0130 (1.66×10^4)	Mo^{VI} , Co^{II} , Bi^{III}
5.	Sn^{IV} , pyrocatechol violet, Tween-20, cetyltrimethylammoniumbromide, pH 1.6–2.7 (with glycine buffer), <i>N</i> -(carboxymethyl)- <i>N'</i> -(2-hydroxyethyl)- <i>N,N'</i> -ethylenediglycine, colour development time 30 min ^d	– (660)	0.0012 (1.03×10^5)	Bi^{III} , Sb^{V} , Ti^{IV} , Mo^{VI}
6.	Sn , 1-[2,3,4-trihydroxybenzene]-4-benzoic acid (TKAB), nonionic surfactant OP, 0.2 M HCl ^e	– (482)	0 0041 (2.86×10^4)	–
7.	Sn^{II} , 0.05–0.10 M HCl, hydrazine sulphate, ferron ^f	TBA-chloroform (390)	0.020 (5.934×10^3)	Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , Zr^{IV}
8.	Sn^{II} , 0.05–0.055 M HCl, ascorbic acid, isoamylxanthate ^g	Chloroform (350)	0.0130 (1.66×10^4)	Mo^{VI} , Co^{II}
9.	Sn^{II} , 0.045–0.070 M HCl, 0.2% CHPB in acetone ^h	Carbon-tetrachloride (415)	0.0030 (3.92×10^4)	37 metal ions do not interfere

^aRef. 1, ^bRef. 2, ^cRef. 3, ^dRef. 4, ^eRef. 5, ^fRef. 8, ^gRef. 9, ^hproposed method.

ues of other parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance were : 0.045–0.07 M HCl, 1.3–4.5 ml of CHPB (0.2% in acetone) and 5–300 s equilibration time for $\leq 20 \mu\text{g Sn}^{\text{II}}$ per 10 ml aqueous volume (Table 1). The order of addition of the reagent and water should be the same as per proposed procedure, otherwise the absorbance decreases on changing the order.

The metal complex obeyed Beer's law in the range 0–2.0 $\mu\text{g Sn}^{\text{II}} \text{ml}^{-1}$ and showed deviation from linearity for $> 2 \mu\text{g Sn}^{\text{II}} \text{ml}^{-1}$ concentration. The Ringbom plot⁶ between percentage transmittance and log ppm of tin showed the optimum concentration for determination of the metal ion to be 0.35–1.90 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 415 nm were $3.92 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0030 \mu\text{g Sn cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The ratio of Sn^{II} and CHPB in the extracted species was determined as 1 : 2 by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper⁷ for a two-phase system and also by mole ratio method.

Effect of diverse ions : Under optimum conditions of the procedure in 10 ml aqueous volume (mg amounts in paren-

theses) iodide, nitrate, sulfate, sulfosalicylic acid and thio-urea (100 each); acetate, ascorbic acid, bromide, chloride and tartrate (50 each); thiocyanate (20); dithionite and sulfite (15 each); citrate and carbonate (10 each); phosphate (8); EDTA 'disodium salt' (2.5); oxalate (1); glycerol and H_2O_2 (6% w/v) (1 ml each) were without affect. Among the cations, Al^{III} , As^{III} , Ba^{II} , Cd^{II} , Co^{II} , Hg^{II} , Mg^{II} , Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pb^{II} , Se^{IV} , Sr^{II} and Zn^{II} (10 each); Be^{II} (5); Ag^{I} (1); Cu^{II} and Os^{VIII} (3 each); U^{VI} (2); Ce^{IV} (1); Ta^{V} (0.5); Bi^{III} , Cr^{VI} , Re^{VII} , Ru^{III} and Th^{IV} (0.1 each); Au^{III} , Ir^{III} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{IV} (0.05 each) and Sb^{III} (0.01) caused $\leq 1\%$ error. Fe^{III} , Zr^{IV} , Ti^{IV} , Nb^{V} , V^{V} , Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} did not interfere in the presence of respective masking agents as described under the procedure.

Applications : The wide applicability of the method was tested by the analysis of several synthetic (some of them analogous to tungsten brass, magnalium cast Z, kneiss metal and argental) and gun metal sample with satisfactory results. The proposed spectrophotometric method is sensitive and highly selective as it is free from the interference of a large number of metal ions especially Fe, Cu, Ag, Zn, Cr, Pb, Mn, Co, Ni, Ti, V, W, Th, U, Mo, Zr, Nb, Re, platinum

metals as well as many other important elements. The relative standard deviation of the method was found to be 0.53%. The proposed method is better than the existing methods^{1-5,8,9} particularly in respect of rapidity, sensitivity and/or selectivity (Table 2).

Table 3. Analysis of tin(II) in different samples

Sl. no.	Composition (mg)	Sn added (μg)	Sn found* (μg)
1.	Cu (1.8), Zn (1.020), Al (0.084), Ni (0.023), Mn (0.021), W (0.06) ^{a,b1}	6.0	5.9 \pm 0.94
2.	Al (0.3), Mg (0.005), Cu (0.001), Pb(0.002) ^{b2}	10.0	9.8 \pm 1.09
3.	Zn (0.040), Pb (0.042), Cu (0.003) ^{b3}	15.0	14.9 \pm 0.73
4.	Cu (0.170), Co (0.01) ^{b4}	15.0	15.2 \pm 0.40
5.	Co (5), Ba (4), U (0.1), Mo (0.08) ^c	10.0	9.7 \pm 0.61
6.	Cd (3), Fe (0.1), V (0.1) ^d	16.0	15.9 \pm 0.54
7.	Sr (2), Cr (0.05), Ag (1), Zr (0.1) ^e	14.0	13.9 \pm 0.78
8.	Pb (2), Nb (0.01), Th (0.03) ^f	12.0	12.1 \pm 0.50
9.	As (2), Se (5), Ti (0.1) ^g	18.0	17.8 \pm 0.36
10.	Re (0.05), Ta (0.01), Bi (0.02)	5.0	5.0 \pm 1.14
11.	Gun metal	9.8% ^h	9.5% \pm 0.62

*Average of triplicate analyses. mean \pm % RSD ($n = 3$).

^aIn presence of 8 mg phosphate. ^{b1, b2, b3, b4} Correspond to tungsten brass, magnalium cast Z, kneiss metal and argental, respectively. ^cIn presence of 15 mg dithionite. ^dIn the presence of 50 mg ascorbic acid. ^eIn presence of 1 mg oxalate. ^fCertified value.

Experimental

UV-Vis (Shimadzu 140-02) spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched glass cells was used for the routine absorbance measurements and spectral studies. The standard stock solution (250 ml) of tin(II) containing 1 mg ml⁻¹ of the metal ion was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount (0.475 g) of SnCl₂·2H₂O (Ranbaxy) in 20 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid (9.6 M), diluting with deionized water up to the mark and standardized by the SnO₂ method gravimetrically¹⁰. Lower concentration at $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level was prepared by suitable dilution of this solution containing 0.5 M HCl final acidity. The containers of the tin solution were wrapped with carbon paper and kept in dark place. Stock solutions of other metal ions were prepared at mg ml⁻¹ level by dissolving their commonly available sodium or potassium salts in deionized water or dilute acid. They were suitably diluted to give $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level concentration of the metal ions. 6-Chloro-3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (CHPB; m.p. 168–170 °C) was synthesized by the literature method¹¹ and dissolved in acetone to give 0.2% (w/v) solution. The chemical composition of CHPB is C₁₅H₉O₃ and its structure is

(CHPB)

Carbon tetrachloride (Ranbaxy) was used as such. Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing tin solution with solutions of various metal ions in suitable proportions so as to give the composition as shown in Table 3.

Dissolution of gun metal : A weighed sample (0.2 g) of gun metal was dissolved in 10 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid (9.6 M) and 2–3 ml of concentrated nitric acid (15.6 M) on heating and the volume was made up to 100 ml in a volumetric flask. 10 ml of this solution was diluted to 100 ml to get a working solution of low concentration. An aliquot (0.5 ml) of this solution was analyzed by the proposed method.

Procedure : To 1 ml aliquot of the sample solution containing $\leq 20 \mu\text{g Sn}^{\text{II}}$ in 0.5 M HCl, were added CHPB 0.2% (w/v) in acetone (1.5 ml) and enough deionized water to raise the aqueous volume to 10 ml in a 125 ml separatory funnel. It was then equilibrated once with 10 ml of carbon tetrachloride for 30 s and the yellow coloured organic layer was passed through Whatman filter paper (No. 41, 9 cm diameter, pretreated with carbon tetrachloride) to remove water droplets, if any. The absorbance of the organic extract was then measured at 415 nm against a similarly treated reagent blank. The amount of tin was determined from the calibration curve plotted under identical conditions of the procedure.

Modifications of the method for the samples containing Fe^{III}, Ti^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, Nb^V, V^V, Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} : for each of 1 mg of Fe^{III} and V^V, 50 mg ascorbic acid; 0.5 mg of Ti^{IV}, 0.1 mg of Zr^{IV} and W^{VI}, 8 mg sodium phosphate; 0.1 mg of Nb^V, 1 mg oxalate and for 0.1 mg of Mo^{VI}, 1 mg sodium dithionite were added prior to the addition of CHPB in 10 ml of aqueous volume.

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